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“ISLA DEL FUEGO: THEN AND NOW”

Two decades ago, Siquijor was once tagged as the island of witches and sorcerers. Many were afraid to set foot on the island, except for the locals. Few knew that the nickname "Mystic Island" truly captured the essence of Siquijor—not because of superstition, but because of its untouched natural wonders. The island, the smallest in the entire Philippines, located in the Visayas region, was brimming with beauty carefully preserved by its people.

As a local, I can still recall how deeply connected the people were to nature. Farming and fishing were the primary forms of livelihood. Only a few locals were professionals or working abroad. Neighborhoods were close-knit, where borrowing a takal of rice, a few matchsticks, or some salt was common. People would simply return what they borrowed once they restocked. Children played freely in the middle of the streets during full moons, as there were hardly any vehicles passing by.

I still remember how, during times when we had no viand on the table, we would simply walk to the beach during low tide. There, we would gather sea shells or sea urchins, which we paired with rice or boiled banana or cassava, and enjoy our meal by the shore. On lucky days, when fishermen had a bountiful catch, they would generously toss us freshly caught fish, which we would later grill over an open fire. Life was hard, but it was simple and less complicated—filled with small joys and shared abundance.

Progress and urbanization were slow on this small island, but the people loved it nonetheless. Life was simple yet happy. The island only became lively during fiesta celebrations, when it came alive with sports events like basketball, volleyball, and larong lahi, along with lively discos and festivities. These were the rare occasions when locals took a break from their daily farming and fishing routines.

Fast forward to today, the once serene and mystical island has slowly transformed into a bustling tourist destination. The island, once secluded, has now opened its gates to travelers from all over the world, captivated by its beauty and tranquility. The turquoise waters, pristine beaches, and enchanting waterfalls have become magnets for visitors.

Seeing the island's growing potential, investors have flooded in, buying large parcels of land from the locals. Restaurants, resorts, spas, inns, and other establishments are sprouting like mushrooms after a storm. RORO vessels and other shipping companies, owned by major investors, now operate regular routes from neighboring provinces, bringing in even more tourists. When locals board these vessels or fast crafts, they

sometimes feel like strangers in their own land, surrounded by foreigners—Chinese, Europeans, Americans, Koreans, and tourists from various regions in the Philippines.

The island, once associated with "mambabarang" (sorcerers) and "manghihilot" (folk healers), is gradually shedding its mystical reputation and becoming more like popular tourist hubs such as Boracay and Bohol. As a result, many locals have shifted their livelihood from farming and fishing to tourism-related jobs—working as tour guides, sales clerks, waiters, or attendants. Job opportunities that once required migrating to larger cities are now available on the island itself.

However, the influx of private vehicles—motorcycles, vans, tricycles, and multicabs—has transformed the once peaceful streets into bustling thoroughfares. Gone are the days when only the chirping of crickets, the singing of birds, and the crowing of roosters at dawn filled the air. Moreover, the once quiet island, known for its near-zero crime rate, is now slowly witnessing incidents of snatching, robbery, and theft. Will these crimes escalate as the island continues to grow in the coming years?

While tourism has undoubtedly brought economic growth and employment opportunities, it also raises concerns. What will happen to Siquijor ten or twenty years from now? Will it still be a hub of culture and tradition for most Siquijodnons, or will it be completely transformed into a commercialized, city-like setup? With locals continuously selling their land to investors enticed by attractive offers, there is a growing fear that they may one day become squatters on their own island.

Progress is not inherently bad, but the preservation of culture and tradition is vital. These values, deeply rooted in the Siquijodnon identity, make the island unique. Siquijor, both then and now, must remain true to its core—protecting its heritage while embracing growth. Only by doing so can it keep its soul intact amidst the winds of change.